

Managed Precarity: The Political Instrumentalisation of the Community Work Programme in South Africa

CJ Tchawouo Mbiada

Department of Mercantile and Private Law, University of Venda Thohoyandou South Africa

With fanfare and trumpet, the South African government launched the Community Work Programme (CWP) in 2007. The CWP is a governmental employment programme initiative that aims to reduce unemployment and underemployment among people with some work. The CWP is a feature of the Expanded Public Works Programme (EPWP), a more comprehensive strategy to reduce poverty and unemployment. This paper critically examines the CWP and argues that while it represents a temporary palliative to disenfranchised populations, it formalises or enacts a sort of labour vulnerability that fails to tackle the structural roots of unemployment. Relying on legal and policy frameworks and literature, the paper demonstrates that CWP participants are subjected to poor wages, insecure employment, and limited employment growth possibilities in addition to often being denied full labour protections. In addition, local political leaders often use the programme to increase their patronage networks, which reduces its ability to foster growth and personal economic sustainability. This study, applying a political economy perspective, concludes that the CWP serves as a device for political scoring and social control rather than a mechanism for formal employment. On this basis, the paper advocates for a reconsideration of public employment programmes that foster dignity, legal protection and a sustainable, inclusive economy.

Keywords: Expanded public works programme, community work programme, unemployment

Post-apartheid South Africa is marred by an unprecedented unemployment rate. It is one of the most significant economic challenges that all successive governments to date have failed to tackle efficiently, notwithstanding two decades of repeated policy interventions geared toward job creation. It is alarming to observe that the country continues to experience appallingly high unemployment rates, especially among the youth, women and rural populations. Statistics South Africa (2025) reveals that the official unemployment rate stands slightly above 31% for the fourth quarter of 2024, while the expanded unemployment rate, made up of discouraged job seekers, in the fourth quarter of 2024 remained unchanged at 41.9% when compared with the third quarter of 2024 (Statistics South Africa, 2025). These rates are not merely statistical variances; they are the product of a deep, inherited structural crisis rooted in historical inequalities. Consequently, the 2025 State of the Nation Address highlighted South Africa's urgent labour market issues, with unemployment remaining a national priority (<https://www.statssa.gov.za/?p=18028>).

In response to this predicament, the South African government has implemented a host of public employment programmes. The visible facet of this programme is the Expanded Public Works Programme (EPWP) launched in 2004 as a poverty and unemployment-driven relief initiative. As part of this general initiative, the government introduced the Community Work Programme (CWP) in 2007 as a key initiative designed to provide

intermittent work opportunities to previously disadvantaged unemployed individuals. Its scope relates to useful activities such as community cleaning, care work, food gardening and infrastructure maintenance.

The purpose of the CWP is to improve the living conditions of the poor in marginalised areas through the provision of work opportunities, experience, skills development and economic participation (Mogale, 2022, p. 30). This signifies that CWP provides participants with income support, work experience and an entry point into the labour market (Mogale, 2022, p. 31). Indeed, participants in the CWP have been able to generate some income, though insufficient to cater for all their needs. They consequently wish to work more days to supplement their income (Langa & Von Holdt, 2011, p. 262). However, a growing concern has been that CWP perpetuates underemployment, sustains low wages and entrenches precarious labour arrangements. More worrisome is the fact that CWP may be susceptible to politicisation, elite capture and corruption (Mogale, 2022, p. 31; Langa & Von Holdt, 2011, p. 272).

It is on this basis that this paper joins the debate with a critical analysis of the CWP through the lenses of labour precarity and political instrumentalisation. The paper argues that the CWP's intended purpose is more akin to a mechanism of political control than a transitioning employment mechanism to alleviate poverty. More so when participants are structurally excluded from the rights and protections afforded to formal employees under South African labour law. Moreover, local political elites use the programme as a tool of patronage, rewarding allies and punishing dissenters.

This contribution uses a political economy method to examine the institutional, legal and political scopes of the CWP. The paper first sets the two barometers (precarity & political instrumentalisation) of the theoretical basis for the analysis. In the second place, the paper examines the legal and economic vulnerabilities of CWP participants. It then investigates the political forces that influence access to the scheme and erode its validity. The paper concludes with

Author Note

CJ Tchawouo Mbiada, Senior Lecturer, Department of Mercantile and Private Law, University of Venda Thohoyandou South Africa
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Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to
CJ Tchawouo Mbiada, Senior Lecturer, Department of Mercantile and Private Law, University of Venda Thohoyandou South Africa
E-mail: carlos.tchawouombiada@univen.ac.za

a set of policy recommendations aiming at changing the CWP from a control mechanism to a genuine tool for social protection and economic development. In so doing, the paper advocates for governmental employment policies that go beyond short-term relief measures to provide long-term solutions which address the root causes of unemployment and the structural barriers faced by marginalised populations in South Africa.

Conceptual Framework: Precarity and Political Instrumentalisation

Before examining the conceptual framework that underpins this paper, it is prudent to briefly state that in post-apartheid South Africa, unemployment, especially among the youth, is a national emergency. Young people are more prone to unemployment as they struggle to find employment in a job market that requires experience. Overall, the official unemployment rate was slightly above 31% for the fourth quarter of 2024, while the expanded unemployment rate, in the fourth quarter of 2024, remained unchanged at 41.9% (Statistics South Africa, 2025). Hence, Bischoff argues that the unemployment crisis in South Africa is a 'ticking time bomb' and that the July 2021 unrest in KwaZulu-Natal and Gauteng evinced the extent of the exasperation of unemployed South Africans (Bischoff, 2023, p. 74).

In tackling the unemployment crisis in the country, South Africa has devised a litany of initiatives. Chief among them is the CWP, which is an extension of the EPWP. The aim of the CWP is to link the divide between social and economic policy (Webster, Fakier, & Metcalfe, 2014, p. 298). In 2007, under a partnership between the Presidency and the Department of Social Development, a CWP pilot programme to test the approach was implemented.

The CWP arose from the limitations of the EPWP, which provided only short-term jobs with minimal long-term impact. Many EPWP beneficiaries returned to unemployment after their contracts ended. In contrast, CWP offers ongoing, part-time work as a form of employment safety net in marginalised areas. It ensures predictable earnings by guaranteeing participants two workdays per week or 100 days annually (Langa & Von Holdt, 2011, p. 259). The CWP is a community-based programme adopted to fight structural unemployment and provide social protection in South Africa (Philip, 2013, p. 6). According to Langa and Von Holdt (2011, p. 259), the implementation of CWP in South Africa was inspired by the National Rural Employment Guarantee Act in India. The CWP is a constitutional strategy that provides decent short- to medium-term work opportunities at a minimum wage to the unemployed (CoGTA, 2018).

It is undeniable that the CWP has been beneficial to the communities, as evinced by the case of Bokfontein. The CWP provides regular part-time work that ensures a stable income, helping to alleviate poverty and hunger in areas with few employment opportunities. Through the creation of jobs for women, youth and foreign nationals, the CWP fosters inclusion and reduces unemployment (Langa & Von Holdt, 2011, p. 268). Additionally, CWP initiatives are designed to meet local needs like home-based care, food growing, water supply and road construction, thus fostering community growth and improved infrastructure. The programme also fosters social cohesion by engaging community members in collective projects, which strengthens interpersonal relationships and reduces societal divisions. Additionally, the CWP

plays a role in violence prevention by helping communities address collective trauma and reduce xenophobia through shared goals and cooperative work. It empowers participants by instilling a sense of dignity and productivity, allowing them to make meaningful contributions to their community (Langa & Von Holdt, 2011, p. 266).

Notwithstanding the above, the CWP faces several challenges. While the CWP offers short-term relief, its long-term impact on structural unemployment and marginalisation remains limited. More so when low wages can frustrate participants by failing to address their ongoing poverty concerns. Lastly, taking into account the possibility that the programme might be captured by local elites, this paper argues that the programme in the long term creates precarity and is politically instrumentalised (Langa & Von Holdt, 2011, p. 272; Mogale, 2022, p. 31).

Hence, this paper draws from the theories of labour precarity and political instrumentalisation to examine the dynamic underpinning the concept of the CWP. These interconnected theories offer a critical lens through which to analyse how governmental employment programmes, though designed to alleviate unemployment, can reproduce structural inequalities and become mechanisms of political control.

Labour Precarity

The notion and paternity of the precariat is attributed to Guy Standing. According to Standing, precariat denotes an emerging socio-economic category of employees who have the same employment features, i.e., uncertainty in social identity, income and work. The precariat is underpinned by temporary employment, low salaries, lack of labour protection, and lack of clear career paths or access to comprehensive social benefits, contrary to the traditional working class, which has historically benefited from permanent employment, stable wages and union protections (Standing, 2014, p. 973).

This group, which comprises part-time employees, interns, migrants and contract employees, suffers from seven types of insecurity: labour market, employment, job, work, skill reproduction, income and representation security (Standing, 2011, p. 16). These uncertainties collectively deprive the precariat of not only material well-being but also a sense of stability and purpose, rendering them more vulnerable to economic challenges and unable to participate meaningfully in political and social life (Standing, 2014, p. 971; Frase, 2013, p. 13).

According to Standing, the precariat differs from other social groups (2011, p. 15) in that they lack the labour protection associated with the traditional privileges that belong to the middle class or the proletariat. Crucially, precarity is a systemic phenomenon influenced by the emergence of gig and platform economies, the deterioration of post-war welfare structures and the flexibility of labour markets. Hence, the relevance of a precariat, in a volatile labour market, lies in constantly engaging in unpaid tasks, including networking, retraining and platform rating improvement (Standing, 2014, p. 965). This perpetuates a cycle of disempowerment characterised by social misunderstanding, job alienation, community separation and income instability.

Moreover, the precariat is devoid of a cohesive occupational identity, which historically provided the working class with a sense of solidarity, pride and political agency. This class is fragmented across lines of age, gender, ethnicity and immigration status, with little shared experience to mobilise around (Standing, 2014, p. 972).

Migrants, for instance, usually comprise a significant number of the precariat and may lack access to even basic legal protections or civil rights, rendering them denizens (someone who has a more limited range of rights than citizens do) rather than full citizens (Standing, 2011, p. 23; Standing, 2014, p. 972). This loss of rights, civil, socio-political, cultural and economic, is not merely symbolic; it fundamentally weakens the ability of the precariat to demand structural changes or advocate for improved conditions.

This means that the precariat's conditions are profound. While Standing (2011, p. 35) cautions against viewing the precariat as a passive or victimised underclass, he also acknowledges the dangers posed by its political disengagement or misdirection. The lack of institutional representation and communal solidarity leaves the precariat susceptible to the allure of populist and authoritarian ideologies, which promise recognition and stability without addressing the root causes of precarity. This vulnerability is compounded by feelings of anger and frustration that stem from blocked social mobility, degraded work environments (Standing, 2014, p.972). This paper argues that this lack of mobility generates a pervasive sense of being left behind more so in an increasingly digital and competitive global economy.

Despite the theoretical robustness of Standing's model, several scholars have criticised its universality. For instance, Munck (2013) argues against the generalisation of the concept of the precariat. The author posits that the precariat is best suited to a capitalist economy context and that its transposition to the Global South may not be appropriate. Munck criticises the Global North's narrative of precarity as a novel condition. He points out that in the Global South, there is a normalisation of institutionalised informal, insecure and exploitative labour. He argues that any analysis of the precariat must be context or region-specific. In the Global South, account must be taken of the role of colonial legacies, structural adjustment policies and persistent inequalities in global trade and labour regimes.

Nonetheless, the importance of the precariat lies in its ability to explain the experiences of millions caught in precarious work. Precariat describes the destruction of labour dignity and the divide between categories of employees in the labour market. Overall, the precariat represents a critical challenge to contemporary labour systems. Its existence reflects the consequences of neoliberal economic policies that prioritise market efficiency over social stability and individual well-being (Standing, 2014, p 44).

In the South African context, the rise of precarious work is deeply rooted in both historical and contemporary forces. Apartheid-era job reservation policies, combined with post-apartheid neoliberal reforms such as the Growth, Employment and Redistribution (GEAR) strategy of the late 1990s, are contributing factors to the informalisation of labour that have weakened and rendered workers vulnerable (Mongale, 2022, p 27). This is so because, for instance, GEAR, which aims to foster a competitive and fast-growing economy, create sufficient jobs and redistribute income and opportunities, has failed to liquidate the Apartheid legacy of job exclusion. Despite the adoption of a host of progressive labour legislation, such as the Labour Relations Act 66 of 1995 (LRA) and Basic Conditions of Employment Act 75 of 1997(BCEA), vast sections of the population remain in forms of work that fall outside the parameters of these legal frameworks (Bischoff, 2023, p75).

To this end, this paper argues that the CWP fosters precarious jobs. This is so because, while framed as a developmental and participatory initiative, the CWP institutionalises precarity by

classifying CWP workers as participants rather than employees. The categorisation of CWP workers as participants effectively excludes them from the protection of the LRA and BCEA. In terms of these laws, only employees defined as '(a) any person, excluding an independent contractor, who works for another person or for the State and who receives, or is entitled to receive, any remuneration; and (b) any other person who in any manner assists in carrying on or conducting the business of an employer' (section 213 of the LRA) are protected. This means that CWP workers do not have the right to form and/or join a union, to collectively bargain and not to be unfairly dismissed or be subjected to unfair labour practices. Further, low wages and part-time structures perpetuate subsistence-level living, where state programmes replicate exploitative informal conditions under the guise of social protection (Nzimakwe, 2008, p. 212).

An illustrative case, although in the context of the EPWP, nevertheless relevant for our purpose, is that of *Working on Fire (Pty) Ltd v National Union of Metalworkers of SA and others* (2022) 43 ILJ 2764 (LAC). Working on Fire (WoF) is part of the EPWP, a government initiative aimed at providing temporary employment to alleviate poverty and equip participants with skills for entry into the formal job market. WoF employed approximately 5,620 workers stationed at 203 bases across South Africa. Only 13% (742 workers) were members of the National Union of Metalworkers of South Africa (NUMSA). Firefighters employed by WoF earned R107.24 per day, which was above the EPWP minimum wage of R88 per day but still significantly below the national minimum wage. NUMSA argued that these wages were insultingly low, exploitative and failed to reflect the dangerous and essential nature of firefighting work (*Working on Fire (Pty) Ltd* para 12).

In 2017, NUMSA sought a 12% wage increase, allowances for working away from home and a subsistence and travel (S&T) allowance. WoF refused to negotiate, citing its contractual obligation to adhere to wage rates set by the Department of Environmental Affairs (DEA). At this juncture, the paper argues that the refusal to bargain was informed by the fact that WoF did not recognise NUMSA as a bargaining agent due to the fact that its workers were not employees in terms of the legislation. Nonetheless, NUMSA referred the dispute to arbitration. The arbitrator adopted a hypothetical approach and ruled in favour of maintaining the status quo, reasoning that WoF lacked the authority to change EPWP wage rates and that NUMSA's demands were unsupported by evidence (*Working on Fire (Pty) Ltd* para 11).

On appeal to the Labour Appeal Court (LAC) following a review by the Labour Court of the arbitration award, the LAC upheld WoF's appeal, thereby confirming the arbitration award. Relevant for our purpose is the fact that the LAC emphasised the importance of the EPWP as a programme designed as a poverty relief initiative, providing temporary employment to unemployed individuals to carry out socially useful activities (*Working on Fire (Pty) Ltd* para 45). The court found further that the EPWP was not intended to compete with the formal job market. Despite the acknowledgment of EPWP's significance, the court acknowledged that WoF's employment model had deviated from the original EPWP design, ie a temporary unemployment relief measure. It had become a permanent yet insufficient unemployment relief programme. The case revealed that many firefighters had been employed for the long term rather than temporarily. Some had been employed for periods as long as 11 years (para 42). The court acknowledged the conditions

faced by firefighters, including the high level of skill, training and physical fitness required for their work. However, it noted that the wages were not commensurate with the work as they were set by the Department of Environmental Affairs based on budgetary constraints and job creation targets, and WoF had no authority to alter them (*Working on Fire (Pty) Ltd*, para 49).

This case illustrates the precarity of the work performed under the EPWP. This programme, intended to provide temporary relief and the skills for recipients to enter the labour market, has become of tool for permanent employment or long-term employment, albeit on less favourable employment conditions and terms. On this basis, employees who have been in the programme for over a decade have worked without being afforded the statutory benefits granted to permanent employees. These employees are in an insecure working condition, which Standing correctly terms the precariat. Indeed, their low wage, limited bargaining power and lack of social benefits are the characteristics of Standing's precariat concept (Standing, 2014). The implementation of the EPWP has in fact, institutionalised the precarity of employment. Hence, in the *Working on Fire* matter, NUMSA had sought a 12% salary increase, even though WoF's employees earned above the daily wage of the EPWP, yet below the national minimum wage (*Working on Fire (Pty) Ltd*, para 52). This evinces the precarious nature of EPWP, which this paper argues is an inherent feature of the programme design at its inception.

Similarly, CWP participants are excluded from standard labour protections due to their classification as 'participants', not employees. Hence, in *Ekuhuleni Metropolitan Municipality v Madonsela and others* (2021) 42 ILJ 2168 (LAC), which related to the EPWP but is instructive for purposes of this paper, the court was called upon to determine the security of employment for workers employed under fixed-term contracts and the application of deeming provisions under sections 198A and 198B of the LRA (*Ekuhuleni Metropolitan Municipality*, para 7). In this case, the municipality employed employees under its EPWP through fixed-term contracts for cleaning and maintenance work. During the second employment period, a contract was concluded between the employees and Hlaniki Investment Holding (Pty) Ltd (Hlaniki) and Gauteng Enterprise Propeller (GEP). Hlaniki was engaged inter alia to manage the services to the GEP (*Ekuhuleni Metropolitan Municipality*, paras 5-6). GEP was engaged to coordinate a job creation programme in which the employees were supposed to participate. The project was initiated by the appellant as a short-term measure to alleviate poverty and unemployment through a job creation scheme.

When the employees' employment was terminated, they referred to a dispute concerning the confirmation of their employment status by the municipality pursuant to s 198A of the LRA (paras 6-7). In determining the dispute, the court ruled that the employees had been unfairly dismissed during the first employment period but were not deemed employed permanently during the second period due to the absence of a tripartite relationship (*Ekuhuleni Metropolitan Municipality*, para 41).

Again, this case raises the issue of the security of employment faced by EPWP employees. The lack of security of employment leaves EPWP or CWP participants in a precarious situation as they cannot receive the benefits afforded to permanent employees and they do not have full legislative protection. On this note, Standing's concept of precariat resonates correctly with CWP participants. Moreover, the fact that NGOs and municipalities act as implementing agents further obscures accountability (Wiltshire,

2016, p. 3).

In addition, CWP participant faces economic insecurity and income insufficiency. As indicated above, and despite government claims of poverty alleviation, CWP stipends fall below the national minimum wage. According to Moeti (2013), participants earn less than half the statutory hourly rate. The cap of two working days per week prevents income generation and reinforces long-term dependency (Thwala, 2008, p. 108).

Another challenge CWP participants encounter is professional stagnation and a lack of upward mobility. Because the essence of the CWP is to provide temporary relief for unemployed citizens, an unintended consequence is the paucity of professional growth for participants. The CWP programme was not designed for that effect. It is a programme designed to provide unskilled and repetitive tasks which do not require a formal training certification (Thwala, 2011, p. 6018) the overall aim is to equip participants with skills the labour market needs. Hence, this paper argues that the CWP fails to provide meaningful career prospects (Fakier, 2014, p. 142) thereby limiting mobility.

Lastly, labour precarity within the CWP must be situated in developing countries within the broader discourse on informal and formal forms of employment, i.e., standard and non-standard employment (International Labour Organisation, 2016, p. 15). According to the ILO, precarious work is characterised by unstable employment relationships, such as social protection, job security and representation (ILO, 2016, p. 17). The CWP, by design, reflects these realities. The part-time nature of the work, the exclusion from formal protections, and the absence of career prospects and full-time employment align closely with what Fakier (2014, p 142) refers to as care workers. Moreover, the precarisation of work within the CWP has gendered dimensions. According to Fakier (2014, p. 134; 137), women make up a disproportionately large number of CWP employees because of their existing caregiving roles in families and communities. Therefore, without changing the structural conditions that make women economically vulnerable, the programme leverages this unpaid care labour and repackages it as public employment. This insight is crucial for understanding how the CWP reproduces gendered labour hierarchies under the guise of empowerment.

Overall, this paper has demonstrated that, although the CWP is envisaged to be a vector of creation of temporary employment for unemployed and marginalised citizens, the unintended consequences are that the programme perpetuates job insecurity, lack of mobility and social protection. In so doing, the programme institutionalises precarity within the vulnerable sector of the population. As CWP participants are in precarious work conditions, they are susceptible to political manipulation.

Political Instrumentalisation of the Community Work Programme

The theory of political instrumentalisation refers to the appropriation of state programmes by political actors to consolidate power, reward patronage and maintain electoral dominance. In South Africa, the CWP has increasingly been implicated in such practices. This is so because the CWP's decentralised model of promoting local participation and flexibility through ward councillors, community development workers and NGOs creates fertile ground for political gatekeeping and elite capture (Langa & Von Holdt, 2011, p. 272).

Empirical studies reveal that political loyalty often determines access to CWP opportunities. Programme recipients are frequently selected based on their allegiance to dominant political parties, particularly the African National Congress, instead of need or merit. This pervasive pattern has grown over time, to the extent that partisan manipulation of participant lists and work allocation are prevalent especially in municipalities where unemployment and poverty create high dependency on public works programmes (Langa & Von Holdt, 2011, p. 272). In this context, the CWP functions not only as a welfare mechanism but also as an instrument of political mobilisation.

The politicisation of the CWP undermines its participatory and developmental objectives and does not promote inclusive development. Hence, community members often report that those thought to be opposition supporters are omitted or illegally removed from participant lists. Such practices not only undermine but also infringe the principle of political neutrality that underpins public service and erode the legitimacy of the state's employment initiatives. Furthermore, they contribute to the erosion of participatory governance by teaching community members how to navigate local political landscapes cautiously by suppressing any dissenting views to gain access to livelihoods (Langa & Von Holdt, 2011, p. 272).

Such survival mechanisms are crucial because local political actors are gatekeepers, using the CWP as a tool for disciplining and rewarding residents. To this effect, ward councillors and politically connected individuals exercise discretion over who is included or excluded from programme participation (Langa & Von Holdt, 2011, p. 272). This undermines the objectivity of the programme and allows political elites to entrench their influence within communities. In places with weak institutional oversight, such practices are institutionalised to such an extent that the CWP becomes a patronage network.

These interfaces generate psychosocial trauma for participants. Wiltshire (2016, p. 9) emphasises that CWP workers often experience feelings of invisibility, disposability and fatigue. Rather than instilling dignity and purpose, the programme frequently reinforces a sense of marginalisation. Participants are well aware that their inclusion is subject to loyalty to the ruling party and that expressing dissatisfaction or aligning with political opposition may cut off their livelihoods. This conditionality fosters a form of managed precarity where recipients are simultaneously protected and exploited by the state.

Legal ambiguity exacerbates this condition. Implementing agents, quite often under-resourced NGOs, are contracted by the state to manage CWP operations, but they cannot enforce uniform labour protections. Moeti (2013) found that many NGOs were unclear about their contractual obligations to participants, leading to inconsistent practices across municipalities. In so doing, it has become difficult to hold programme administrators accountable for misconduct or negligence. The decentralised governance of the CWP has become both a source of flexibility and a structural weakness, fuelling exploitation.

The political instrumentalisation of the CWP is most visible during electoral cycles. Reports from participants indicate that programme access is used to influence voter behaviour. Persons are reportedly forced to attend party rallies or have their participation in the programme terminated due to their perceived political

affiliations. This is described as soft coercion where beneficiaries are compelled to demonstrate political loyalty to maintain access to basic subsistence (Langa & Von Holdt, 2011, p. 272). Hence, public employment becomes a form of vote-buying, which severely compromises the integrity of democratic participation.

Besides the effects on participants, this politicisation destroys the legitimacy of local governance institutions. As monitoring and evaluation mechanisms are weak, and grievance redress processes are rarely effective, the CWP's institutional credibility suffers, and its capacity to function as a genuine developmental tool is diminished.

The conditionality of CWP participants to align with political affiliation creates a sense of what Langa and Von Holdt refer to as insurgent citizenship, in terms of which access to socio-economic rights is mediated through political patronage. This undermines democratic norms and creates a political culture of dependency and fear. Langa and Von Holdt's (2012) concept of insurgent citizenship describes this narrative well: individuals are politically engaged, but only within the confines of patron-client networks that delineate the boundaries of acceptable participation.

It is at this junction that the paper argues that labour is a commodity in violation of the ILO 1944 Declaration of Philadelphia. The principles espoused in the Declaration underscore the inherent dignity of human beings and their right to freedom and well-being. Labour cannot be treated as a tradable good or service. CWP participants have become a tool at the disposal of politicians who trade work opportunities under the CWP for electoral gains. Because of the high rate of unemployment in South Africa, unemployed marginalised persons, whether young or old, succumb to this type of tradership. Despite South Africa being a welfare state, how the CWP is implemented leads this paper to contend that its participants are indeed commodities in a manner consonant with neoliberal states. Indeed, Supiot argues that neoliberalism's focus on labour as a tradable entity has led to moral, social and environmental crises (2021, p. 3).

According to Supiot, labour, land and money are treated as commodities under capitalism, despite being fundamental conditions for production and trade (2021, p. 3). Labour cannot be separated from the worker, as it involves physical, intellectual and historical commitments unique to each individual (2021, p. 6). Moreover, the employment contract reduces work to a monetary exchange, where workers trade their time for wages without rights over the products of their labour. In so doing, the trade-off reduces labour to a commodity to which a monetary value is attached. The monetary value ascribed to each labour varies and Supiot argues that neoliberal policies have exacerbated inequality, precariousness and environmental degradation, while reducing work to a financial transaction. Thus, CWP participants, whose labour is valued below the minimum wage rate, trade their labour at a reduced or ridiculous rate. This trade-off fosters inequality and precarity to the extent that the meagre wage or pittance that CWP participants earn monthly is insufficient to sustain them.

The paper has thus far demonstrated that the political instrumentalisation of the CWP reflects general challenges of governance in South Africa with the entrenchment of patronage politics, the erosion of institutional integrity and the failure of public employment programmes to fulfil their developmental objectives. Although the CWP was designed as a transformative initiative, its

co-option by political actors has limited its impact and exacerbated social inequality.

The Illusion of a Solution: CWP and Structural Unemployment

This paper argues that the CWP entrenches job insecurity and is a recipe for political instrumentalisation. The paper contends that, notwithstanding its objectives to create jobs and alleviate poverty among the vulnerable section of the society, the CWP fails to address the structural foundations of South Africa's unemployment crisis. Nevertheless, the programme can be credited with providing short-term economic relief to a limited number of participants. However, the programme does not function as a genuine labour market catalyst mechanism; instead, it covers up the scale of unemployment, normalises underemployment and reproduces the very economic marginality it purports to alleviate. On this basis, this paper argues that the CWP is not a sustainable employment solution.

In the first place, the CWP in South Africa has evolved from a short-term employment relief scheme into a structurally embedded form of institutionalised underemployment. Initially intended to provide participants with part-time employment while allowing space to pursue other economic activities, the CWP now effectively locks individuals into a cycle of low-income work. Participants are capped at two working days per week, a design choice that fails to reflect the realities of South Africa's labour market, where additional employment opportunities are scarce. This is especially detrimental because CWP recipients are low-skilled people with no formal education, and CWP work has become their sole source of income, with some participants expressing the desire to work for more days (Langa & Von Holdt, 2011, p. 262). As a result, rather than facilitating labour mobility, the CWP has become a vector for managing poverty through the rationing of work. This creates an institutionalised system of economic marginality in which the participants are paid just enough to survive without an avenue towards achieving self-sufficiency or sustainable livelihoods.

This is institutionalised underemployment, where the state normalises a parallel section of underutilised labour that is excluded from the mainstream economy. This workforce, largely made up of black South Africans, remains excluded from formal recognition, skills development opportunities or career progression. The absence of structured training, enterprise support and placement services further entrenches the programme's failure to offer a developmental pathway. The so-called work experience provided under the CWP is neither formally accredited nor widely accepted by employers, undermining any real potential for participants to move into decent work.

A second fundamental flaw lies in the CWP's compensation structure. Participants are paid stipends significantly below the thresholds established by the National Minimum Wage Act 9 of 2018. For instance, CWP workers earned R81 per day, which is equivalent to R10.12 per hour over an eight-hour day, despite the minimum wage standing at R28.79 per hour. This discrepancy sends a regressive message about the value of the labour provided by poor communities, undermining both the legal and moral imperatives of fair labour practices. Section 23 of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996 enshrines the right to fair labour practice, but the state circumvents this by classifying the CWP as a developmental initiative rather than formal employment. This rhetorical manoeuvre

allows the government to bypass labour law obligations while simultaneously benefiting from participants' contributions to community services and infrastructure.

Equally worrisome is the programme's failure to function as a stepping stone into the formal economy. Effective public employment schemes should enable participants to transition into more stable and better-paid jobs. However, government data rarely reflects post-programme outcomes, and independent assessments suggest that most CWP participants do not move beyond the scheme as they struggle to find permanent jobs (Langa & Von Holdt, 2011, p. 262). While the CWP may instil a work rhythm, this alone is insufficient for labour market integration. The programme lacks coordination with vocational training systems, local economic development strategies and national employment planning. It is largely isolated from the broader economic ecosystem that could otherwise support upward mobility. Additionally, the statistical treatment of CWP participants as employed distorts the true scale of unemployment in official data, masking systemic joblessness and painting a misleading picture of policy success.

Finally, the growth of the CWP reflects a broader policy failure: it serves as a substitute for comprehensive industrial and employment strategies. South Africa's economy continues to suffer from capital intensity, deindustrialisation and weak demand, yet the CWP is used as a stopgap to absorb surplus labour. Instead of addressing structural constraints or investing in job-generating sectors such as manufacturing, infrastructure and services, the state relies on public employment as a palliative measure. Moeti (2013, p. 28) contends that the CWP resembles a social welfare mechanism more than a genuine employment intervention. In the context of fiscal austerity and restrained public investment, the programme becomes a politically expedient tool to manage discontent rather than to transform the economy. Ultimately, the CWP reflects a low-ambition model that stabilises poverty without challenging the root causes of inequality and unemployment.

Recommendations: Toward Dignified and Transformative Public Employment

This paper argues for a redesign of the CWP so that it aligns with South Africa's constitutional commitment to dignity, equality and social justice. First, regarding status, CWP participants should be recognised as employees. In so doing, they would benefit from legislative protections, collective bargaining rights, access to dispute resolution mechanisms and the minimum wage.

Second, recruitment processes must be transparent, fair and depoliticised. Reliance can be placed on the EPWP Recruitment Guidelines, particularly clause 6.1, so as to ensure that recruitment is based on merit, and is transparent and inclusive. There is a need to establish oversight mechanisms, such as regular audits and independent grievance channels, that would thwart political interference and corruption.

Third, the CWP should include a solid skills development framework linked to local economic development plans. This would involve partnering with the Sector Education and Training Authority and TVET colleges, for instance, to provide accredited training. Aligning training with the labour market demand equips and prepares CWP participants for labour mobility. By aligning work experience with demand-driven skills, the programme would increase participants' opportunities to secure sustainable livelihoods beyond the CWP.

Lastly, the wage structure must be re-evaluated in line with the National Minimum Wage Act 9 of 2018. A restructured payment model that allows full-time work or flexible options with proportional compensation should be considered to ensure a living wage. This would help to move the programme from a subsistence-level safety net towards an inclusive employment strategy.

Conclusion

The CWP was conceived to address South Africa's systemic unemployment, combining the goals of poverty alleviation and social cohesion. However, this paper has demonstrated that the CWP falls significantly short of reaching these objectives. Instead of offering a meaningful bridge to the formal economy or a path towards decent work, the programme institutionalises underemployment, marginalises its participants through legal ambiguity and operates as a mechanism for political control.

The design of the CWP, made up of part-time work, stipends and the absence of legal protections, places it firmly within what Standing has termed the precariat. Participants are not only economically vulnerable but also politically subordinate, subject to patronage networks and gatekeeping by local elites. Far from uplifting communities, the programme has instead enabled elite capture, with access to work frequently conditioned upon political loyalty. In this way, the CWP has become not an empowerment vehicle, but a tool for absorbing submissive populations while avoiding the difficult structural reforms needed to create inclusive economic growth.

This paper, therefore, argues that the CWP currently does not deal with the root causes of unemployment or economic exclusion in South Africa. Instead, it acts as a form of managed precarity, placing the unemployed within a minimalist welfare vicious cycle that fails to challenge the structural foundations of inequality. To move beyond this impasse, public employment must be radically reimagined.

What is required is a paradigm shift of public employment initiatives, which treat participants not as beneficiaries but as workers entitled to fair wages, formal protections and opportunities for growth. Thus, CWP participants should be recognised as employees so that they have legislative protections such as access to dispute mechanisms and minimum wage compliance. On the political front, local elite must be insulated from recruitment and oversight mechanisms so as to avoid capture, thereby ensuring transparency, fairness and community ownership rooted in democratic norms rather than patronage.

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